

CO-OPERAS workshop

FAIR data and Social Sciences and Humanities

Coimbra December 6, 2019

Programme

14:00-14:30 Who are we? Informal presentations

14:30-15:00 Introduction: OPERAS, Co-OPERAS, FAIR principles (Delfim Leão, Maria Manuel Borges)

15:00-16:00 Focus Group (plenary): define “data” in the SSH

16:00-16:30 Individual exercise: how FAIR are the data I produce/use?

16:30-17:00 Sharing results of the individual exercise

Participants

21 researchers; disciplinary areas:

Digital Humanities

History

Portuguese Studies

Library and Information Science

Chemistry

Botany

SOME ISSUES THEY AGREED ON (IN GENERAL)

- **metadata are crucial, and they cannot be separated from data**
- **to assure interoperability is crucial**
- **need of ontologies, thesauri, metadata standards, persistent URLs...**
- the exercise on the level of FAIRness was really appreciated, in spite of the fact that none of them uses data on a daily basis since they are just beginning their PhD.

First session

FOCUS GROUP ON DATA IN THE SSH

Lively discussion trying to agree on a common definition of data.

Some of the proposed definitions:

- data and metadata are inseparable
- some data require codification to assure anonymity
- raw data have no sense
- in some disciplines like neuroscience, data can be an electro biological signal
- data is the least quantity of information that one can have and alone its value is almost zero
- data is all the collected information that, once analyzed, can bring information to be used along with research
- data are previous information, an element that combined with others generates information from a cognitive point of view

- data allow us to collect information to our users (bibliographic information)
- data are in a context
- data acquire meaning through context and use.
- to be reusable, data must be in the context
- data have several senses and potential information, but they only give information when I attribute them some kind of sense. There are two kinds of information, potential and real.
- data are something collectable that generates information
- when we apply a survey, we are dealing with an instrument, the answers are data and the interpretation of data is information
- a set of data is information
- only when data are in a context they can give us information
- data have value in a context
- context and data give us information
- data are data, what changes is the context
- data should be put in context and preserved
- data have multiple senses, there are different kinds of data, mathematical and other, data have multiple senses
- when data have sense, meaning, they are information
- data are organized by metadata schemes
- what is the meaning of data and metadata? metadata are data about data
- do data have a potential of meaning?
- data are different in different disciplines
- the process is important - generation, producing, creation - and the first context that data have is the need for formatting to be recognized by the systems, any system. Another sense can be found if we consider data as a process, that is, data collected by a system and put in context in a system
- historical data are formalized and can be contextualized. Not all historical data can be formalized but those that are can be shared and reused
- what we are looking for is to register all this information with the maximum possible meaning
- what is the research object? This is the question that guides us to the following about data, context, use and information
- we have data and research data and research data need to be planned before the research starts

Some conclusions on which all of the participants agreed

- The definition of data is dependent on the disciplinary area
- Data have different natures
- It is almost impossible to find a definition on which everybody can agree

Second session

WHAT WE THINK OF “FAIR”

- it's mostly a matter of **awareness, training sessions are needed**
- **R-Reuse is the final goal**
- There are no **incentives for researchers to share their data**

GENERAL ISSUES AFTER THE EXERCISE ON FAIRNESS

Since most of them are in an early stage of research, the discussion was more around FAIR principles than their practices as researchers. Being, in the majority, Information Science PhD students, they are very aware of the problems that the lack of tools can cause to get FAIR data, namely:

FINDABLE

- lack of thesauri or authority files to enable content search
- lack of indexes
- lack of unique identifiers or standards
- lack of quality in metadata

ACCESSIBLE

- data are fragmented in several sources

INTEROPERABLE

- need of ontologies, vocabularies and specialized authority files

REUSABLE

- copyright is the main issue and there is a need to clarify who owns what
- lack of skills to associate the appropriate license
- need of legal advice on use and reuse